

First Steps Towards a Cable-Driven Parallel Robot for Naval Operations

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Abstract—This paper focuses on the study of a cable-driven parallel robot (CDPR) for the automated handling of payloads from a ship. Handling operations are performed at sea, under calm to mild weather conditions, thus both the payload and the ship (on which the robot is installed) may possess oscillatory motions. The tasks the robot has to perform are (i) payload autonomous tracking and picking on the sea surface, and (ii) payload lifting. Robot and task modelling are introduced, as well as the controllers used to achieve such operations.

Index Terms—Cable-driven parallel robots, marine robots, sea robots, winches

I. INTRODUCTION

Cable-driven parallel robots (CDPRs) are manipulators moving an end-effector (EE) thanks to extendable cables, that are connected in a parallel fashion. CDPRs effectively act as multiple, fast, and coordinated cranes, concurring in the dexterous manipulation of the EE. Their industrial application are multiple: entertainment [1], logistics [2], construction [3], maintenance [4], and inspection [5], just to name a few.

The use of CDPRs in marine handling tasks, where the robot frame or the cargo to be picked are subject to wave motion, has recently attracted a lot of attention [6], [7], [8], [9], [10], [11], [12], [13], [14] due to CDPR intrinsic autonomy and enhanced motion capabilities with respect to standard or gantry cranes, which are less dexterous and need to be operated and assisted by specialized workforce. Multiple cables can (i) dexterously manipulate a picking apparatus, mounted on the robot EE, so that the cargo can be dynamically captured while floating at sea level, and (ii) avoid or drastically limit cargo oscillations during lifting and transportation. Previous research aimed at designing completely or redundantly restrained manipulators, even though the task to be performed usually require translational motion of the EE only. Additional control capabilities are used to slightly adjust the EE orientation for picking operations, and to more easily compensate for wave-induced actions on the robot. Unfortunately, the use of many cables imply a higher robot cost, but more importantly a higher maintenance complexity; the latter reason is especially critical for marine manipulators, where equipment reliability is

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Figure 1: UACDPR schematics (cables in black, EE in red)

of utmost importance, and maintenance cost is severe due to intervention limitations.

In this paper, we introduce an underactuated cable-driven parallel robot (UACDPR) for cargo handling, and its functionalities for operating from a ship side. The UACDPR uses less cables than the degrees of freedom (DoFs) of its EE, but its capable of large controlled translational motions, while maintaining its EE orientation within feasible limits thanks to dedicated controllers [15], [16], [17]. The robot EE is an automated hook, equipped with sensory equipment dedicated to cargo tracking, and it is designed so as the payload can be picked even in presence of mild misalignments ($\sim 10^\circ$ on tilt and yaw angles of the EE). In the following, system modeling, controllers, and operation capabilities are briefly summarized.

II. MODELING

The UACDPR considered in this paper consists of a mobile platform (or EE) coupled to the base by $n = 5$ cables (Fig. 1), coiled by servo-actuated winches. $O_S x_S y_S z_S$ is a frame attached to the robot, and thus to the ship where the robot is mounted, while $P x' y' z'$ is attached to the EE. l_i ($i = 1, \dots, n$) is the length of each cable, which is the distance between the cable exit point from the frame D_i and the cable attachment point A_i onto the EE. The cable direction is denoted by \mathbf{t}_i , and depends on the relative distance between O_S and P , denoted by \mathbf{p} , and also on

Figure 2: Ship kinematic model, CDPR installation location (in green), and EE (in red)

the robot frame and *EE* frame orientations, respectively denoted as θ_S and θ and expressed according to the roll-pitch-yaw convention.

The ship on which the robot is mounted is modelled as a rigid body, subject to a specific motion pattern due to common sea-ship interaction modelling assumptions (Fig. 2): the translational motion along the x_S axis (*surge*) is assumed to have an approximately constant velocity during robot operation, whereas the translational motion along the y_S axis (*sway*) and the yaw motion are approximately null; on the other hand, the motion along the z_S axis (*heave*), roll, and pitch are approximately sinusoidal, and their amplitude and frequency depend on the sea state and ship type.

The CDPR *EE* is considerably small with respect to (w.r.t.) workspace dimension by design, and cables are attached approximately in the same point on the *EE*. Thus the CDPR dynamic model can be simplified, by considering the *EE* as a point-mass:

$$m\ddot{\mathbf{p}} = -\sum_{i=1}^4 \mathbf{t}_i \tau_i - \mathbf{t}_5 \tau_5 + m\mathbf{g} = -\Xi \boldsymbol{\tau} - \mathbf{t}_5 \tau_5 + m\mathbf{g} \quad (1)$$

$$\Xi = [\mathbf{t}_1 \ \cdots \ \mathbf{t}_4], \quad \boldsymbol{\tau} = [\tau_1 \ \cdots \ \tau_4]^T, \quad \mathbf{g} = -9.81\mathbf{z} \quad (2)$$

where τ_i is the i -th cable tension, m is the *EE* mass, and \mathbf{z} is a unit vector directed as the earth gravity. Rotational *DoFs* of the *EE* are disregarded, but, in practice, their dynamics act as a disturbance on the translational dynamics, and needs to be compensated by the controller.

Depending on the task to be performed by the *EE*, a control law for the system inputs, namely the array of cable tension $\boldsymbol{\tau}$, is determined so as to achieve the desired system response. Once a control law for $\boldsymbol{\tau}$ is established, cable

tensions are converted into cable velocities and fed to low-level drive controllers [18].

III. CONTROLLERS

The CDPR needs to perform two primary tasks, namely (i) autonomously track and pick an object on the sea surface, and (ii) lift an object from or deploy it to the sea surface. The first task naturally becomes an *EE* trajectory-tracking problem, while the second one is more similar to a standard crane operation, and the additional robotic capabilities are used to stabilize the load during lifting. A particular requirement for this application is to decouple the behaviour of the 5 cables: the lateral cables are operated differently than the central one, exiting from $D_5 \equiv O_S$ and attached in P . Lateral cables are used for the dynamic control and the stabilization of the *EE*, whereas the central cable, or lifting cable, is kept slack during tracking and is only used to support the *EE* weight during lifting.

A. Tracking controller

In the implementation of the tracking controller, the central cable is slackened prior to control activation, thus imposes a negligible disturbance on the *EE* dynamics. The aim of the lateral cables is to displace the *EE* so as to track the object to be picked. The tracking feedback controller computes the acceleration \mathbf{u} required by the *EE* for tracking the object, and is thus in the form:

$$\boldsymbol{\tau} = m\Xi^+ (\mathbf{g} - \mathbf{u}) + \lambda \Xi^\perp \quad (3)$$

where Ξ^+ and Ξ^\perp are, respectively, the Moore–Penrose inverse and the nullspace of Ξ ; λ is a free parameter that can be optimized so as to maintain cables taut without modifying the translational dynamics of the *EE* [19].

In order to measure the relative distance between the *EE* and the object \mathbf{e}_p , which is needed to compute the control action \mathbf{u} , several measurement devices were tested in order to achieve the optimal compromise between accuracy, refresh rate, latency, and equipment cost. A stereo-camera was used in the end, and a coloured feature on the object to be picked was recognized with a dedicated software. The main problem in the use of such a sensor is the poor refresh rate: \mathbf{e}_p was sampled at 15 Hz, while the robot control algorithm needs to run at 1 kHz for optimal tension-regulation results. Nonetheless, by suitably interpolating \mathbf{e}_p between samples, a signal to be sampled at 1 kHz $\mathbf{e}_{p,int}$ could be obtained, and the regulator was given by a simple PID controller:

$$\mathbf{u} = k_P \mathbf{e}_{p,int} + k_D \dot{\mathbf{e}}_{p,int} + k_I \int \mathbf{e}_{p,int} \quad (4)$$

where k_P , k_D , and k_I are controller constants to be tuned.

Since the controller in Eq. (3) requires the computation of Ξ , the relative position between the *EE* and the ship frame should be estimated. Additionally, the ship frame orientation (pitch and roll parameters, since yaw is assumed not to vary during operation) is also needed for projecting

Ξ onto a global inertial frame. The latter task was accomplished by mounting a VRU (Vertical Reference Unit, or dynamic inclinometer) which could provide roll-and-pitch parameters at a sample rate of 400 Hz with an accuracy of 0.3° . Position estimation, instead, was achieved by *CDPR* direct kinematics [20].

B. Lifting controller

In the implementation of the lifting controller, the central cable is velocity commanded as the lifting cable of a standard crane, so that (approximately) a lifting velocity profile can be imposed on what the *EE* is transporting. The lateral cables, instead, are used to dissipate any motion other than the lifting one; the control objective can be stated as to reach zero cable speed when the lifting operation is completed, and thus also the lifting winch is braked. A simple model-less controller achieving such a task is given by:

$$\boldsymbol{\tau} = \boldsymbol{\tau}_0 + \gamma \Xi^T \dot{\mathbf{p}} \quad (5)$$

γ is a scalar quantity, and is indeed a damping coefficients for the *EE* dynamics, while $\boldsymbol{\tau}_0$ is simply a mean cable tension to be maintained at equilibrium. The higher $\boldsymbol{\tau}_0$, the stiffer and more responsive the motion dissipation of the robot, but the higher the power consumption. The intuitive reason why this very simple controller works lies in the kinematics of the robot:

$$\Xi^T \dot{\mathbf{p}} \approx [\dot{i}_1 \quad \dots \quad \dot{i}_4]^T \quad (6)$$

and the controller in Eq. (5) simply varies the cable tensions so that cable velocity reach zero, that is, a stationary *EE*. The controller is thus effectively implemented as:

$$\boldsymbol{\tau} = \boldsymbol{\tau}_0 + \gamma [\dot{i}_1 \quad \dots \quad \dot{i}_4]^T \quad (7)$$

As a last remark, please note that in case the computed tensions surpassed some imposed upper and lower limits, the values assigned to the low-level controller was saturated to the limit in order to prevent damages to the robot or cable involuntary slackening during operation.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL TESTING

A prototype of the system was developed, whose frame horizontal dimension was $2 \text{ m} \times 2 \text{ m}$, and with 5 m available vertical depth. The 5 winches were positioned at the corners and in the center of the frame, and cables attached to an experimental automatic hook, developed in a separate study (Fig. 3). A payload was located on a shuttle that could perform linear motions at 45° w.r.t. the horizontal plane, and a red marker was attached to it, so that a camera system, mounted on the *EE*, could detect it.

The phases leading to the autonomous tracking and picking of an object are hereby reported to show the capabilities of the developed system. From a homing configuration, the *EE* is *deployed* to a configuration suitable for the camera to start detecting the payload, by using only the lifting controller: the central cable is unwound to

Figure 3: *Experimental Layout*

a prescribed length, while the lateral cables stabilize the *EE* ($t = 0 \dots 25$ s in Fig. 4). Then, lifting-controller outputs and tracking-controller outputs are averaged for 10s so as to smoothly transition from the lifting controller to the tracking controller. At around 35s the actual trajectory tracking starts, and it can be clearly seen in Fig. 4 that the *EE* is able to rapidly minimize the tracking error, and maintain it bounded. Please note that, for picking reasons, the z -coordinate fed to the controller is offset by 0.5m, so that the payload can be picked by "dropping" on it.

The stabilized lifting of the picked payload was also tested, but the experimental apparatus was not completely representative of the final application: in fact, the grasped payload could only be approximately the same weight of the *EE* due to installed power limitations, while the real application would require the robot to stabilize a payload weighing approximately 250 times more than the *EE*. In our lab demonstration, the payload and the handler were stabilized without overshooting.

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Figure 4: Autonomous tracking experimental results: the EE position is in black, while payload position, as reconstructed with the camera system, is in red.

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